

The Normal and the Psychological: A Theoretical Opposition

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Summary

Orlando Villas-Bôas, in his testimony recorded in the documentary *Don Quijote de la Selva* (1998), observed: *"We have found a stable, tranquil society, a society where no one commands anyone. [...] In our modern society governed by economic, productive and commercial processes, we do not have the slightest resemblance to humans in their natural environment."* This statement synthesizes the fundamental contrast between the human "normal" — evidenced by balanced indigenous societies — and the "psychological," an artificial construction arising from the hierarchical and economic pressures introduced in post-agriculture.

This essay explores the historical and biological transition that shaped human conditions, highlighting how the advent of agriculture and institutional hierarchies fragmented the social and emotional balance that defined 96% of the history of the species. Anthropological references, such as those of Gallois and Scott, and biological studies on

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oxytocin and Dunbar's number, support the analysis that the "psychological" is an adaptive deviation from natural pressures. In addition, *Orquiza's work The Price of Life* is used to demonstrate how the contemporary economic cycle transforms human energy into a commodity resource, amplifying the artificial conditions that sustain the "psychological".

The essay concludes that modern psychology must abandon the humanocentric view of the "psychological" as the norm and rediscover the "normal," represented by the natural dynamics of small human groups in equilibrium. To move forward, it is essential to integrate biological and anthropological approaches that prioritize social and emotional harmony. This essay, however, is limited to presenting fundamental critical premises that question the contemporary psychological paradigm, without offering definitive solutions, and it is hoped that these reflections will serve as a starting point for the academic environment to develop alternatives based on the human "normal".

Keywords: Normal, Psychological, Natural pressures, Post-agriculture, Small groups, Oxytocin, Dunbar's number, Indigenous knowledge, Social fragmentation, Human-centric construction, Social harmony.

Introduction

For 96% of human history, populations lived in small hunter-gatherer groups, characterized by ecological balance and population stability. These groups, amply documented by anthropological and ethnographic studies, presented a cohesive social organization, governed by natural

pressures that shaped norms of cooperation and harmony (Lee & Daly, 2005). Reciprocity and the absence of rigid hierarchies guaranteed a harmonious and sustainable coexistence, consolidating what can be called the human "normal".

By contrast, the advent of agriculture about 10,000 years ago, accounting for only 4 percent of the total time of human history, brought drastic changes. This transition inaugurated the need for domestication not only of plants and animals, but of the human species itself. The introduction of hierarchies and the expansion of more complex social structures have resulted in social fragmentation and the emergence of the "psychological." This historical anomaly reflects the disruption of the natural pressures and social equilibrium that characterized small human groups for most of evolution. This phenomenon, widely explored in literature such as *Against the Grain* (Scott, 2017), reflects a disruption with the evolutionary balance and is evidenced by growing inequality, conflicts, and the emergence of modern diagnostic categories, such as those described in the DSM-5.

Important Note: Psychology, since its formation, has neglected to understand the human "normal" based on an evolutionary and natural perspective. Instead, it was anchored in the paradigm of the "psychological", a historical abnormality originating in post-agriculture. This approach, centered on fitting individuals to artificial systems, ignores the inherent balance seen in small communities free of rigid hierarchies and interpersonal conflicts. Studies such as those of Gallois (*O Jardim dos Zoé*, 2005) and the testimony of Villas-Bôas in the documentary *Don Quijote de la Selva* (1998) reveal that the human "normal" is evidenced in indigenous communities, where harmony and the absence of psychological pathologies are the norm.

This essay aims to oppose the "normal" and the "psychological" by exploring the historical, biological, and social conditions that underpin these concepts. Starting from an analysis of the centrality of the oxytocin molecule in human social functioning, of the cycle "from zygote to zygote" (Orquiza, 2024), and of the limits imposed by the cognitive capacity described by Robin Dunbar (1992), the text also examines contemporary phenomena, such as the behavior of "no one enters anyone's house", which reflect biological adaptations in a world of artificial pressures. The conclusion proposes a revision of psychology, recognizing the "normal" as the primary and sustainable state of humanity, and approaching the "psychological" as an adaptive construct to modern social and economic deviance.

Central Thesis

The "psychological", as a predominant phenomenon in modern psychology, is not an intrinsic characteristic of humanity, but an artificial and historical construction that emerges from the hierarchical, social and economic pressures introduced by post-agriculture. In contrast, human "normal," evidenced by 96 percent of the history of the species, reflects a state of social and biological harmony in small groups governed by natural pressures. This essay argues that psychology, by ignoring the "normal," perpetuates a humancentric logic that adjusts individuals to maladjusted systems, rather than questioning the structures that give rise to modern pathologies. By exploring the biological dynamics of oxytocin, the impact of the economic cycle described in *The Price of Life*, and the testimonies of balance in

indigenous societies, this text proposes an epistemological revision of psychology to rediscover the human essence in the "normal".

This essay does not intend to offer a definitive alternative proposal to modern psychology. Instead, its objective is to present robust and grounded premises, which serve as a basis for academic reflections and debates, encouraging the collective construction of proposals that review the epistemological bases of the discipline.

The Normal: Evolutionary Harmony and Natural Pressures

1. Definition of Normal

For most of human history, small social groups have lived under natural pressures that have shaped cooperative and harmonious behaviors. These groups, composed of about 30 to 150 individuals, reflected a social organization intrinsically adapted to human cognition and biology, as described by Dunbar (1992). Studies such as those by Lee and Daly (*The Cambridge Encyclopedia of Hunters and Gatherers*, 2005) highlight that societies such as the San (South Africa) and the Hadza (Tanzania) lived in balance with the environment, operating with a system of reciprocity and cooperation.

The absence of rigid hierarchies in these groups allowed for a harmonious relationship between individuals and the environment. Resource management was shared, avoiding significant inequalities and promoting ecological sustainability. As highlighted by Jared Diamond in *The World Until Yesterday* (2012), these groups did not face chronic

interpersonal conflicts, common in hierarchical societies, but worked together in a model that prioritized collective well-being.

- *Quote:* "Hunter-gatherer societies have social networks marked by reciprocity and the absence of rigid hierarchies, ensuring intragroup harmony and ecological sustainability" (Lee & Daly, 2005, p. 78).

This harmony, based on spontaneous cooperation and limited social networks, was a reflection of the evolutionary pressures that shaped human beings. What can be called human "normal" is directly related to this small-scale social dynamic, in which the balance between social interactions and the surrounding environment was maintained without the need for artificial control mechanisms.

Connection with Modern Harmony

These examples, both biological and social, reinforce that the human "normal" is sustained by small groups and high-quality social interactions. The modern fragmentation, which arose after the advent of agriculture, is a direct reflection of the disruption with these natural conditions. Understanding the "normal" from this evolutionary and biological perspective is essential to criticize modern maladjustments and propose solutions that prioritize social and emotional harmony.

This solid foundation demonstrates that natural pressures and human biology are the main forces that sustain the "normal," creating a direct contrast to the hierarchical and artificial systems that sustain the "psychological."

2. The "Zygote to Zygote" Cycle

As argued by Orquiza (2024) in *From the Zygote to the Zygote*, the oxytocin molecule plays a central role in maintaining this "normal". This molecule, which regulates social bonds and prosocial behaviors, is directly linked to the perpetuation of DNA and the functioning of small groups.

The "zygote to zygote" cycle describes human biological and social functioning as a sequence rigidly programmed to ensure reproduction and survival. In this cycle, biological energy is efficiently coordinated, reinforcing the viability of DNA as a central protagonist of life.

- *Quote:* "DNA emerges as the essential protagonist of existence, while organisms and cells are transitory instruments subordinated to its viability" (Orquiza, 2024, p. 2).

Oxytocin, essential for group cohesion, ensures not only deep emotional bonds, but also the maintenance of advantageous interactions in small communities. This biological functioning reflects a perfect symbiosis with natural pressures: DNA coordinates the energy and interactions needed to sustain the group, while oxytocin strengthens the bonds that ensure collective survival.

In addition, Dunbar's number, which limits the human cognitive capacity to manage meaningful social interactions to about 150 individuals, reinforces the importance of small groups as the ideal basis for social organization. Larger groups require artificial structures of control, which break with the natural cycle and create social maladjustments.

The Psychological: A Post-Agricultural Detour

1. Emergence of the Psychological

The "psychological", instead of being an intrinsic characteristic of human development, is a historical deviation arising from the social and economic transformations imposed by the advent of agriculture. This humancentric construction seeks to categorize and normalize a vast spectrum of abnormalities, many of which are amplified by the artificial conditions of hierarchical and productive societies. The **DSM-5**, with its almost a thousand pages of diagnoses, exemplifies how modernity tries to organize phenomena that were not observed in the 96% of pre-agricultural human history. At that time, natural pressures and life in small groups structured behaviors in a way that minimized conflicts and ensured emotional stability.

A clear example of this discrepancy is the exponential increase in diagnoses of anxiety disorders and depression, conditions that are practically nonexistent in small group contexts. In these communities, such as the **Zo'é** (Gallois, 2005) and the groups observed by **Villas-Bôas** in the Xingu (1998), emotional needs were mediated by deep and constant social bonds, eliminating the need for complex diagnostic categories. These societies not only demonstrate a social and ecological balance, but also the absence of psychological pathologies, showing that the "psychological" is a modern anomaly.

The population concentration and social hierarchy introduced by agriculture have exceeded the functional limits of human biology. Molecules such as **oxytocin**, which regulate social interactions and strengthen interpersonal bonds, were less effective in large, fragmented populations. This maladjustment resulted in hormonal and behavioral

dysfunctions, aggravated by social inequalities and the centralization of power.

- *Quote:* "The transition to agriculture introduced hierarchical inequalities and institutional dependencies that profoundly transformed human relations" (Scott, 2017, p. 45).

2. The Role of Agriculture in Diversion

Agriculture, by requiring the organization of large human groups, created hierarchical and control structures that broke with the intrinsic harmony of small communities. As discussed in *Against the Grain* (Scott, 2017), sedentary lifestyle and the domestication of production have fueled deep inequalities, marking the beginning of systematic social conflicts and economic exploitation. The emergence of hierarchies meant the imposition of rigid social roles, discouraging community bonds and increasing social fragmentation.

Anthropological and historical studies point out that the first city-states of Mesopotamia exemplify this deviation. With population growth and the need to coordinate resources, dominant elites emerged, forcing individuals to adapt to systems alien to human biology. These systems depended on relentless productivity and institutional controls that turned social interactions into sources of chronic stress.

3. The Psychological as a Consequence

The "psychological" emerges as a survival mechanism in response to the maladjustment created by hierarchical and economic pressures. Anxiety, depression, and other modern pathologies reflect not only the difficulty individuals have in adapting to these conditions, but also the

impacts of disruption to the balanced living patterns that characterized "normal."

In contemporary indigenous societies, such as the Zo'é, where hierarchies are absent and reciprocity is the norm, doctors, psychologists, and psychiatrists are unnecessary (Gallois, 2005). Villas-Bôas' testimony reinforces that emotional and social harmony in these groups is sustained by constant community interactions and the absence of external economic pressures.

This contrast reveals that the "psychological" is a response to the artificial post-agricultural environment, sustained by structures of control and exploitation that break with the natural conditions that have shaped humanity. Therefore, understanding the "psychological" as an adaptive and historical deviation is essential to critique the current model and rethink the foundations of modern psychology.

2. Dunbar and Social Capacity

Robin Dunbar (1992) proposes that the size of the human neocortex limits the number of meaningful social relationships an individual can maintain, estimated at approximately 150. This number, known as "Dunbar's number," reflects the human cognitive and biological capacity to sustain cohesive social bonds in small groups. In hunter-gatherer societies such as the San and Hadza, this limitation was a crucial element in ensuring social harmony, reciprocity, and cooperation, without the need for rigid hierarchies.

Language, as suggested by Dunbar, has evolved as a tool for coordinating interactions and managing larger groups. However, it is insufficient to replicate the deep emotional bonds and interpersonal

trust mediated by molecules such as oxytocin. In small groups, oxytocin strengthens social bonds, facilitating prosocial behaviors and ensuring group cohesion. This biological functionality, however, finds limits in populations that exceed Dunbar's number.

- *Quote:* "The size of the neocortex determines the capacity to maintain cohesive social relations, estimated at 150 individuals" (Dunbar, 1992, p. 685).

In the post-agricultural context, exceeding this limit was inevitable due to population growth and the concentration of people in urban centers. This has resulted in social fragmentation and the need for institutional hierarchies to manage larger groups. Hierarchies have introduced inequalities and created emotional barriers, transforming the natural cohesion of small groups into artificial structures of control.

Anthropological and historical studies, such as those by Scott (*Against the Grain*, 2017), show that early agricultural civilizations faced the challenge of managing large populations. The rise of elites, armies, and bureaucracies was a workable response, but these adaptations destabilized natural social bonds, creating an environment of emotional fragmentation and polarization.

Moreover, the centrality of language in post-agricultural societies, while essential for large-scale coordination, does not replace the face-to-face and emotional interactions characteristic of small groups. The absence of these deep connections has led to alienation and the emergence of psychological pathologies associated with interpersonal disconnection.

Dunbar emphasizes that human cognitive capacity is ideal for contexts of direct interactions and quality relationships, typical of smaller

groups. In larger groups, social pressures and the need to adapt to hierarchical systems create emotional maladjustments that negatively impact mental health. This fragmentation, therefore, reinforces the thesis that the "psychological" is a deviation from natural human conditions.

The inability of modern societies to operate within Dunbar's number exacerbates reliance on external structures, such as economic and medical systems, to address the resulting emotional and social maladjustments. Understanding this boundary is essential to reassess how modern communities can rebuild social bonds and regain lost balance.

3. The Economic Cycle and the Epicenter of the Psychological

The post-agricultural economic cycle, as analyzed by Orquiza (*The Price of Life*, 2024; *The Price of Life*, 2024), transforms human energy into a commodity resource. This process, essential to sustain the inequalities and hierarchies of modern societies, is at the heart of the abnormalities categorized in the "psychological". Whereas in traditional small-group contexts work was a means of collective survival and reciprocity, in the post-agricultural system it has become a commodity, detached from human social and emotional needs.

This mercantile economic cycle fragments social bonds and reinforces a logic of control, creating an environment where pathologies such as anxiety and depression thrive. Orquiza argues that the disconnect between human energy and the natural conditions of "normal" misaligns the biological and social balance that has characterized humanity for most of its history.

- *Quote:* "Without the coordinated, self-regulating energy of individuals, the modern business cycle would collapse, returning to the state of disorganized matter" (*The Price of Life*, 2024, p. 45).

In the contemporary context, the incessant productivity required by the business cycle creates social polarization and interpersonal fragmentation. Human energy, which once operated in harmony with natural and communal cycles, is consumed in an uncoordinated way to power economic systems that prioritize profit over collective well-being. Orquiza describes how this disconnection compromises the functionality of oxytocin, a molecule responsible for modulating prosocial interactions and maintaining group cohesion. The loss of this balance amplifies social isolation and the psychological conditions associated with modernity.

The impact of the post-agricultural business cycle is evident in the replacement of authentic human interactions with relationships mediated by hierarchical and technological systems. In small traditional communities, such as those described by Gallois (*O Jardim dos Zo'é*, 2005), human work was directly connected to collective needs, and social bonds strengthened group cohesion. However, in the modern economy, interpersonal relationships have been replaced by impersonal contracts and reliance on centralized institutions, contributing to the disintegration of social bonds.

In addition, the economic cycle commodifies human subjectivity, transforming emotions, behaviors, and even psychological pathologies into products to be treated or consumed. This phenomenon is evident in the expansion of diagnostic categories in the DSM-5, which reflect the

attempt to manage the psychological consequences of a system disconnected from human biological and social needs.

Orquiza concludes that the modern business cycle not only deviates humanity from its natural bases, but also perpetuates the conditions that sustain the "psychological" as a tool for social control and adaptation to the system. The disconnect between the "zygote to the zygote" and the contemporary economic cycle reinforces social and emotional fragmentation, showing that the "psychological" is more a symptom of a maladjusted system than an intrinsic condition of humanity.

To overcome these challenges, it is essential to rethink the business cycle in terms of harmony with human biological and social needs, recovering the lost balance and restoring the role of human energy as an integrated and coordinated component, rather than as an exploited commodity.

Indigenous Knowledge and the Remnant of the Normal

1. Indigenous Harmony

The balance observed in isolated indigenous communities exemplifies what can be considered the human "normal", a condition characterized by the absence of rigid hierarchies and harmonious coexistence among individuals. Research such as that of Gallois (*O Jardim dos Zo'é*, 2005) and the testimonies of Orlando Villas-Bôas (*Don Quijote de la Selva*, 1998) reveal societies where interpersonal conflicts are practically non-existent, and social reciprocity is a shared norm. In these communities, such as the Zo'é, the social structure is guided by community values and practices that reinforce emotional balance and group cohesion.

"I have never seen an Indian fight with another, I have never seen a husband fight with his wife. [...] These are norms of a highly tranquil society, and ours is a totally unhappy society" (*Don Quijote de la Selva*, 1998).

These groups operate consistently with the social boundary estimated by Dunbar's number, about 150 individuals, where meaningful interactions are maintained, and interpersonal trust is strengthened by repeated and frequent interactions. This eliminates the need for hierarchical systems and institutional control, common in modern societies.

Mental health, in these contexts, is mediated by balanced intraspecific interactions and supported by molecules such as oxytocin, which strengthen social bonds and promote an environment of emotional safety. This biological functionality is optimized in small groups, where the absence of economic or hierarchical pressures allows human relationships to be authentic and meaningful.

2. The Absence of Modern Pathologies

As noted by Gallois (2005), Zo'é peoples live in a social dynamic where anxiety, depression, and other psychological conditions categorized in the DSM-5 are not evident. Reciprocity and the absence of interpersonal competition create an environment where mental health is a natural consequence of social structure. The absence of doctors, psychologists and psychiatrists in these communities reinforces the idea that the "psychological" is a phenomenon conditioned by the artificial pressures of post-agriculture.

3. The Preservation of the Remnant of the Normal

These indigenous groups offer a glimpse into what could be considered a remnant of human "normal," a harmonious state that has been largely replaced by hierarchical and productive systems. Villas-Bôas' testimony highlights that the tranquility observed in these communities is not a utopia, but a condition historically rooted in human social functioning:

"The child is free. [...] The old man is the owner of history, the Indian is the owner of the village, and the child is the owner of the world" (*Don Quijote de la Selva*, 1998).

The preservation of these practices and social structures in isolated indigenous communities provides empirical and anthropological evidence that the "psychological" is an artificial construction, born of the rupture with the intrinsic balance of the human "normal". These examples point to the possibility of rescuing practices that prioritize community cohesion and emotional balance, reducing the impacts of artificial pressures that sustain the "psychological" in modern societies.

2. "Nobody Enters Nobody's House"

The contemporary phenomenon of domestic exclusivity, where individuals prioritize separation and privacy over collective coexistence, reflects an unconscious attempt to recreate the social conditions that allowed human survival for 96% of evolutionary history. In small groups, such as those in hunter-gatherer societies, social cohesion was mediated by frequent interactions, interpersonal trust, and reciprocity, largely underpinned by the functionality of the oxytocin molecule. However, population growth and social fragmentation have

created a scenario in which meaningful ties are replaced by microspaces of exclusivity, such as the home.

While this modern territoriality suggests an effort to preserve deep affective bonds, it also points to the social and emotional fragmentation that characterizes contemporary societies. Domestic exclusivity, symbolized by the maxim "no one enters anyone's house," demonstrates that modern humans try to compensate for the lack of community cohesion through restricted and highly selective interpersonal relationships.

Impacts on Oxytocin Functionality

Human biology remains dependent on the social and cognitive boundaries described by Dunbar's number, where oxytocin plays a key role in regulating meaningful interactions. In contemporary contexts, overcoming these limits and social fragmentation prevent oxytocin from operating effectively on larger scales, reducing its ability to modulate interactions in dense and diverse populations.

- *Analysis:* This behavior suggests that the biological limits of oxytocin continue to operate, even in a culturally and demographically altered environment. However, its effectiveness in modulating broader social interactions has been reduced in the modern context.

Exclusivity as a Reflection of Fragmentation

Domestic exclusivity not only highlights the breakdown of group cohesion in large societies, but also exposes the challenges of living in a world where social connections are often mediated by artificial structures such as digital networks or professional relationships. While

the home remains a space of refuge, the emphasis on exclusivity demonstrates that modern social and economic pressures have undermined the human capacity to operate in broad community networks.

Connection with the Psychological

This behavior also reflects the impact of the "psychological" on modern social dynamics. Anxiety and distrust, amplified by economic pressures and emotional fragmentation, encourage a move away from broader community interactions in favor of more restricted and controlled ties. Contemporary territoriality, therefore, represents both an attempt to preserve affective bonds and an adaptive response to a system that fragments the social and generates emotional polarization.

In short, the "no one enters anyone's house" phenomenon is a modern manifestation of the biological and social limits that have shaped humanity. It exposes the tension between the biological needs for social cohesion and the challenges posed by an artificially overpopulated and fragmented world. Recognizing this dynamic is essential to understanding how modernity broke with the human "normal" and perpetuated the "psychological" as an adaptive deviation from artificial pressures.

Integration of Premises: Oxytocin and Dunbar

The centrality of oxytocin in the zygote-to-zygote cycle demonstrates that human social interactions are regulated not only by cognitive limits, as proposed by Robin Dunbar (1992), but also by profound biological mechanisms. Oxytocin, a molecule essential for maintaining emotional

and social bonding, is designed to operate effectively in small groups, sustaining prosocial behaviors and promoting group cohesion.

Biology as the Basis of "Normal"

In the context of small pre-agricultural groups, oxytocin played a central role in building trust and reciprocity among community members. These bonds were optimized within the limits imposed by Dunbar's number, which estimates at 150 the number of meaningful interpersonal relationships that humans can manage effectively. This boundary is not arbitrary, but is deeply rooted in human biology and evolution, aligning with the neocortex's ability to process complex social information.

The functionality of oxytocin in small groups allowed communities to operate in harmony, minimizing interpersonal conflicts and promoting collective survival strategies. Post-agricultural population expansion, however, has exceeded these limits, requiring the creation of hierarchical structures and institutional systems to manage interaction in large populations. This process resulted in a fragmentation of social ties and emotional polarization, evidencing dysfunction in a system originally programmed for intragroup harmony.

The Post-Agricultural Misalignment

With the advent of agriculture, population expansion and the concentration of people in urban spaces have increased the complexity of social interactions, overcoming the biological limits of cohesion. This misalignment had significant consequences:

1. **Reduced Efficacy of Oxytocin:** In larger, fragmented groups, oxytocin loses some of its functionality as the frequency and

quality of interpersonal interactions decrease. Deep emotional bonds give way to superficial relationships, increasing distrust and social isolation.

2. **Need for Hierarchies:** To coordinate large populations, hierarchical and bureaucratic structures emerged that replaced the natural mechanisms of group cohesion. Although functional in organizational terms, these hierarchies broke with the intrinsic balance of small communities.
3. **Social Fragmentation and Polarization:** The fragmentation of social ties, aggravated by overpopulation, has generated inequalities and conflicts, amplifying psychological pathologies such as anxiety and depression.

Connection with the Psychological

The dysfunction resulting from population expansion and biological misalignment helps to understand the emergence of the "psychological". While oxytocin sustained advantageous interactions in small groups, the post-agricultural context broke with these conditions, exposing individuals to social and emotional pressures that generated modern pathologies. The "psychological", in this sense, can be seen as an adaptive response to a system that has exceeded the natural limits of human cohesion.

The integration of Dunbar's and oxytocin's premises demonstrates that human social functionality is deeply rooted in biological and cognitive limits. Understanding these limits is essential to critique modern social and economic structures and propose alternatives that prioritize the harmony intrinsic to the "normal". Ultimately, this calls for a return to

valuing the natural dynamics that underpin the emotional and social health of the species.

Discussion

The analysis of the "normal" and the "psychological," underpinned by the biological and anthropological concepts presented throughout this essay, reveals a critical disconnect between the conditions that have shaped the evolution of the human species and the demands of modern societies. The discussion emphasizes that the "psychological" is an adaptive deviation resulting from the artificial pressures of post-agriculture, while the "normal" reflects a state of social and biological equilibrium, intrinsic to human functioning in small groups.

1. The Role of "Normal" in Social and Emotional Health

The "normal," exemplified by contemporary indigenous societies and small prehistoric groups, demonstrates that social and emotional health is deeply rooted in natural pressures. These contexts operate in harmony with the limits imposed by human biology, such as Dunbar's number and oxytocin functionality.

In small groups, intragroup cohesion was ensured by repeated, high-quality interpersonal interactions, mediated by reciprocity and trust. This natural model did not require external interventions, such as those described in modern structures of control and psychological treatment. Studies by Gallois (*O Jardim dos Zoé*, 2005) and the testimonies of Villas-Bôas (*Don Quijote de la Selva*, 1998) reinforce that, in contexts of "normality", modern pathologies, such as anxiety and depression, are non-existent.

2. The Post-Agricultural Deviation and the Impact of the Psychological

The transition to agriculture, accompanied by population growth and the introduction of social hierarchies, broke with the natural conditions that sustained the "normal". The increase in social complexity has exceeded biological and cognitive limits, creating inequalities and polarizations that have fragmented interpersonal bonds. In this scenario, the "psychological" emerges as an adaptive construct to systems that are misaligned with fundamental human needs.

The economic cycle described by Orquiza (*The Price of Life*, 2024) illustrates how human energy has been transformed into a commodity resource, creating a system that perpetuates social and emotional fragmentation. This systematic exploitation of human energy not only diverts humanity from its natural bases, but also amplifies the conditions that sustain the "psychological" as a central phenomenon of modernity.

3. Social Fragmentation and Domestic Exclusivity

Phenomena such as "no one enters anyone's house" are evidence of the attempt to preserve meaningful microspaces of interaction in a fragmented social context. This modern territoriality, although it represents an effort to maintain affective bonds, reflects the alienation and distrust amplified by social polarization and interpersonal disconnection. The inability to recreate the balance observed in small groups reinforces the thesis that the "psychological" is a response to the denaturalized environment of contemporary societies.

4. Rethinking Psychology: Reconnecting to "Normal"

Modern psychology, by ignoring "normal" as a primary, sustainable state, perpetuates a human-centric approach that adjusts individuals to maladjusted systems. To move forward, it is necessary for psychology to reconnect with the biological and social foundations that underpin emotional health and social cohesion.

This calls for an epistemological revision of the discipline, incorporating the anthropological and biological evidence presented in this essay. Valuing community practices based on reciprocity and group cohesion, coupled with the recognition of the biological limits described by Dunbar and underpinned by oxytocin functionality, may offer a path to reversing the fragmenting impact of the "psychological."

Conclusion of the Discussion

The "psychological", far from being a universal or intrinsic condition, is a reflection of the artificial pressures imposed by post-agriculture and the modern economic cycle. On the other hand, "normal" represents an ideal state, rooted in human evolution and sustained by the intrinsic harmony of small groups. Reversing the impacts of the "psychological" requires a return to practices that prioritize community cohesion and valuing human biology as the basis for social and emotional health. Only by reconnecting with the "normal" can psychology transcend its human-centric logic and align itself with the fundamental needs of humanity.

This essay is limited to presenting fundamental critical premises that question the contemporary psychological paradigm, without offering definitive solutions. It is hoped that these reflections will serve as a starting point for the academic

environment, in a collaborative and interdisciplinary way, to develop alternatives based on the human "normal".

Conclusion: A Psychology Grounded in the Normal

Modern psychology, as a discipline, faces a fundamental epistemological challenge: to recognize that the "psychological", in its predominant form, is not an intrinsic condition of humanity, but rather an adaptive construct born of the historical deviation imposed by post-agriculture. By neglecting the human "normal," psychology perpetuates a logic that adjusts individuals to maladjusted systems, ignoring the biological and social underpinnings that have shaped the species for 96 percent of its evolutionary history.

Indigenous knowledge and biological perspectives centered on oxytocin offer an alternative path to reorient the discipline. Testimonies such as those of Villas-Bôas (*Don Quijote de la Selva*, 1998) and studies such as those of Gallois (*O Jardim dos Zo'é*, 2005) reveal that the human "normal" is marked by the intrinsic harmony of small groups, where natural pressures shaped prosocial behaviors, ensuring cohesion and sustainability. These practices, observed in societies close to Dunbar's number, demonstrate that emotional and social balance is intrinsically linked to the maintenance of meaningful interpersonal interactions, supported by molecules such as oxytocin.

The post-agricultural business cycle, as argued by Orquiza (*The Price of Life*, 2024), has fragmented the natural bases of human interaction, transforming energy and social relations into commodities. This system not only deviates humanity from its natural bases, but also amplifies social and emotional fragmentation, perpetuating the "psychological" as a tool for adapting to maladjusted conditions.

To move forward, it is essential that psychology reconnects to "normal" by integrating approaches based on intragroup cooperation, reciprocity, and the biological limits described by Dunbar. Valuing these practices does not mean a return to the past, but a review of the premises of the discipline, which must prioritize human balance and abandon the logic of adjustment to artificial systems.

A psychology founded on the "normal" will not only revise its epistemological foundations, but also offer a more integrated and holistic view of social and emotional health. By recognizing the "psychological" as a historical deviation, the discipline can transcend its human-centric logic and align with the fundamental needs of the species, promoting a future where intrinsic harmony is the basis for human development.

References

1. Dunbar, R. I. M. (1992). *Neocortex size as a constraint on group size in primates*. *Journal of Human Evolution*.
2. Gallois, D. (2005). *The Garden of the Zo'é*. São Paulo: Edições Sesc.
3. Lee, R. B., & Daly, R. (2005). *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of Hunters and Gatherers*. Cambridge University Press.
4. Villas-Bôas, Orlando. Interview in the documentary *Don Quijote de la Selva*. *New Atlantis Full Documentaries*, 1998, 58:26. Published on YouTube, June 3, 2013, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=knfSRz1hJrM#t=703>. Accessed on 15 Dec. 2024.
5. Orquiza, J. C. (2024). *Do Zigoto ao Zigoto*. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14451181>.

6. Orquiza, J. C. (2024). *The Price of Life: Your Work, Your Energy, the True Engine of the World Economy*. Author's Edition. ISBN 978-65-01-24960-5. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14421113>.
7. Orquiza, J. C. (2024). *The Price of Life: Your Work, Your Energy, the True Engine of the World Economy*. Author's Edition. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14274282>.
8. Scott, J. C. (2017). *Against the Grain: A Deep History of the Earliest States*. Yale University Press.